

BIOMECHANICAL MODEL OF BONE TISSUE GROWTH IN DIFFERENT CERAMIC SCAFFOLD GEOMETRIES

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1. Introduction

Several bone diseases cause a progressive weakening of bone structures, eventually leading to collapse and often resulting in degenerative arthritis [1]. Currently, few treatments offer both mechanical support and promote angiogenesis. The geometry of these scaffolds plays a key role in influencing cellular behavior and mechanical properties. Therefore, a multidisciplinary optimization is needed. To this purpose, in this study we determined the correlation between the geometrical features and the predicted bone growth capability [2].

2. Materials and Methods

Various hydroxyapatite scaffolds with Diamond, Gyroid, IWP, Primitive, and Lidinoid TPMS geometries have been analysed. Parameters like trabecular thickness (TbTh), spacing (TbSp), and tortuosity vary across designs, while porosity is kept constant at 70%. The mechanobiology model by Nasello et al. [3] was used to systematically assess bone tissue growth and scaffold performance, simplifying cellular invasion as a diffusion process triggered by mechanical stimulus. As diffusion occurs, granulation tissue density increases, causing the Young's modulus to rise. The scaffold-granulation tissue construct was subjected to uniaxial and confined compression, with the model applied to each geometry using finite element software.

3. Results

The granulation tissue progressively evolved to full bone density at different time points for different geometries (Figure 1) depending on the kinetics of the cell population and on the stiffness of the ceramic scaffolds. Consistently the Young's moduli of the granulation tissue for different geometries range from 60 GPa for IWP, Primitive, and Gyroid to 40 GPa for

Lidinoid and Diamond under uniaxial compression

By day 30, tissue density nearly reached its maximum for IWP, Primitive, and Diamond. However, bone tissue in Lidinoid and Diamond geometries did not reach the maximum density under uniaxial compression.

Figure 1: Evolution of the average bone density (g/cm^3) of the granulation tissue in the different TPMS geometries over 84 days (12 weeks).

4. Discussion and Conclusions

Certain TPMS geometries, such as IWP, Primitive, and Gyroid, promote greater bone growth, correlating with a higher Young's modulus. Currently, parameters like TbTh, TbSp, and tortuosity are being studied to assess their influence on the biomechanical behavior of granulation tissue. Although simplified, the developed model will constitute a design an effective tool to optimize scaffolds architectures for mechanical and mechanobiological performances.

5. References

1. Kawai T et al., J Orthop Res; 2017.
2. Yang Y et al., Proc Natl Acad Sci; 119(43): e2211113119 (2022).
3. Nasello G et al., Multiscale Mech Biol Eng; 2023.